

Research Article

Organ Donation awareness among farmers of selected rural area of Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

The study designed to analyze the knowledge and attitudes toward organ donation among farmers and laborers in Andhra Pradesh. Health care workers play an important role in educating and raising awareness about organ donation in a community. In our research of 465 individuals, 136 were female and 329 were male. This cross-sectional survey successfully assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and desire to donate organs. We checked Attitude and the willingness of organ donation by the question Whom would you like to donate to farmers in responded Family member 119 (39.66%) and Laborers 75 (45.45%) and the organ donation to "Any Religion", farmers responded 50 (16.66%) and Laborers 33 (20%). As an Indian citizen with a social obligation to society to assist better people's lives, I checked this criterion using the question Should organ donation be promoted? Farmers opted YES 269 (89.66%), while laborers voted NO 132 (80%). In question: Have you ever donated blood? Farmers 190 (63.33%) chose yes, while laborers 74 (44.84%) chose no. Response to the question "Do you think it's important to bury my body "whole"? 179 (59.66%) farmers and 119 (72.12) laborers said YES. Organizing campaigns and activities to raise awareness about organ donation can assist farmers and laborers improve their knowledge and attitudes.

Keywords: Organ Donation, Awareness, farmers, laborers, knowledge and attitudes.

Introduction

To combat organ trafficking and encourage donation after brain death, the government passed "The Transplantation of Human Organs Act" in 1994, which marked a fundamental shift in India's organ donation and transplantation landscape. The various such programmes are as follows-

- Andhra Pradesh - Jeevandan Programme
- Karnataka – Zonal Coordination Committee of Karnataka for Transplantation
- Kerala – Mritha Sanjeevani – The Kerala Network for Organ Sharing
- Maharashtra – Zonal Transplant Coordination Center in Mumbai
- Tamil Nadu – Cadaver Transplant Programme.

Every year, many people die as a result of ailments including kidney failure, liver failure, heart disease, and blood cancer. They may have led a productive life if they had a donor who could give them organs. Many of these people are unable to get organs from appropriate relatives for a number of reasons. The only option left for them is to obtain organs from a deceased donor [1].

There is a significant gap between the need for transplant organs and the lack of donor organs. Public knowledge of organ donation is strongly proportional to levels of education[2,3]. To develop effective public policies supporting organ donation, it is critical to understand the people's attitudes about the issue. This allows us to identify target groups and modify our tactics accordingly. To boost the organ availability, consistent effort and strategic planning are required. Raising public awareness can greatly increase the number of organ donors. Several studies have investigated socio-demographic differences in attitudes, knowledge, and behavior about organ donation and registration [2].

Organ donation (OD) is a life-saving medical procedure in which organs are taken from donors and transplanted into recipients with organ failure, restoring critical functions, improving quality of life, and decreasing morbidity and mortality. Many patients with end-stage organ failure regard transplantation

as the best and, in most instances, only therapy option [4]. Organ transplantation enhances patient survival and quality of life, and has a significant positive effect on public health and the socioeconomic burden of organ failure[5]. The availability of an appropriate organ is the greatest obstacle in transplantation.[6] However, the primary hindrance to the organ transplantation program worldwide is the shortage of donor organs[7]. Several studies have found gaps in knowledge, attitude, and practice about organ donation among medical students globally, including India.[8-10]. India, like many other countries of the globe, does not have enough cadaveric organs for transplants; as a result of a shortage of donor organs, more than 20% of transplant waiting list patients globally die. Medical students will push for organ donation as future doctors. However, many lack important core information and are impacted by the public's personal beliefs and biases, which affect health care professionalism. Inadequate knowledge, cultural ideas, religious thoughts, misunderstanding, and inability to find potential donors are all viewed as key factors to the organ shortage. Additionally, there is a disparity between attitudes and actions of medical students [11].

Because of an inadequate number of donors, people in need of transplantation have to wait a lengthy period. Patients with end-stage renal illness might remain on dialysis until they get the donated organ. Mechanical devices, on the other hand, cannot sustain patients who require heart, lung, and liver support for a lengthy period of time. As a result, there is a huge need to increase organ donation and the use of donor organs.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional online and offline survey was conducted at the state level between January 2022 and February 2022. This is a cross-sectional study conducted in the rural service area of Sanganapalli is a locality in *Gudupalle, Chittoor*, Andhra Pradesh. Sanganapalli is situated nearby to the locality Bazanipalli and the village

Būragalapalli. The questionnaire was sent via WhatsApp and several media sites. We have included all of the Sanganapalli and surrounding village's farmers and labourers aged 18–49 years. Those who did not reply to all of the questions were excluded from study. A predesigned questionnaire was used to collect data from 265 individuals with n = 465, and farmers 300 & 165 Laborers. The questionnaire consists of two sections: the first is about demographic data, and the second is about questions to assess awareness, attitude,

and beliefs regarding organ donation. Data collected were analyzed using ANOVA and P value was calculated. P value <0.005 was regarded as significant.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 22.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA), and the categorical variables were reported as both a number and a percentage.

Results: Demographic and sociocultural characteristics

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics and awareness about organ donation in the study population

Variable Total n=465	Farmers n=300 (%)		Laborers n=165 (%)		p value
	Aware	Unaware	Aware	Unaware	
Age group (years)					
18-30	155	10	56	2	0.01
31-40	78	9	46	3	
41-49	30	18	39	19	
Gender					
Male	212	19	85	13	0.02
Female	51	18	56	11	
Education					
Uneducated	69	21	97	20	0.3
High school	162	15	35	3	
University Degree	32	1	9	1	
marital status					
Unmarried	194	16	37	8	0.01
Married	10	11	92	12	
Other			12	4	
Cumulative monthly income					
5000 - 20,000	19	6	25	6	0.3
20,000 – 50,000	3	0	0	0	
50,000-80,000 >80,000			0	0	

Table 1 depicts sociodemographic variables and knowledge of organ donation among the study population. Between the ages of 18 and 30, 155 farmers and 56 laborers were aware of organ donation. In the age range of 31-40, 78 farmers and 46 laborers were aware of organ

donation. In the age range 41-49, 30 farmers and 39 laborers were aware of the organ donation.

Table 2 includes eight questions to assess respondents' general awareness about organ donation. "Information about organ donation?"

was the first question. Their responses show a great awareness of the terms organ donation, Farmers: 215 (71.66%), laborers: 39 (23.63%) opted YES. When asked if there is an age restriction for organ donation, most farmers responded Don't know 174 (58%), and labor answered NO 96 (58.18%). The third inquiry questioned which organs may be donated, heart donation, eye donation, skin and liver donation awareness was very high among the subjects farmers and laborers, i.e. heart donation 197 (65.66%) and 139 (84.24), eye donation 297 (99) and 126 (76.36), skin donation 162 (54) and 93 (56.36), and liver donation 257 (85.66) and 103 (62.42) respectively.

"The overall awareness" of all the requested questions concerning donation, in farmer were 216 (72) and labor 97 (58.78) was noted. The response to Question 4 is highly enthusiastic,

Table2: Assessment of respondents' general awareness about organ donation.

Questions	Responses			p Value
		Farmers n=300 (%)	Laborers n=165 (%)	
Information about organ donation?	Yes	215 (71.66)	39 (23.63)	0.001
	No	50 (16.66)	68 (41.21)	
	Don't know	35 (11.72)	58 (35.15)	
Age limit of organ donation?	Yes	69 (23)	21 (12.72)	0.03
	No	57 (19)	96 (58.18)	
	Don't know	174 (58)	48 (20.09)	
What organs can be donated? Kidney	Yes	254 (84.66)	91 (55.15)	0.06
	No	6 (2)	9 (5.45)	
	Don't know	40 (13.33)	65 (39.39)	
Heart	Yes	197 (65.66)	139 (84.24)	0.01
	No	3 (1)	1 (0.60)	
	Don't know	100 (33.33)	25 (15.15)	
Eyes	Yes	297 (99)	126 (76.36)	0.30
	No	0	1 (0.60)	
	Don't know	3 (1)	38 (23.03)	
Bone marrow	Yes	23 (7.66)	21 (12.72)	0.09
	No	167 (55.66)	108 (65.45)	
	Don't know	110 (36.66)	36 (21.81)	
Lungs	Yes	125 (41.66)	39 (23.63)	0.4
	No	79 (26.33)	69 (41.81)	
	Don't know	96 (32)	57 (34.54)	
Skin	Yes	162 (54)	93 (56.36)	0.21
	No	65 (21.66)	52 (31.51)	

i.e., the purpose of organ donation. Farmers relied on it as a responsibility, with 202 (67.33) and laborers 78 (47.27) agreeing to donate an organ to save another person's life.

"Organ donation is Unsafe?" This question is regarding the feeling of participant, farmers and Laborers chosen option Yes 213 (71) and 123 (74.54) respectively. donated organs could be misused? 149 (49.66%) farmers and 61 (36.96%) Laborers answered most.

Would you donate the organ? This is to check the willingness of participants to donate the organ, where 109 (36.33%) farmers said NO and 82 (49.69%) Laborers responded Would definitely want to donate. In question Feels donor not live long, the responses from farmers were 267 (89%) and from Laborers 142 (86.06) as YES.

	Don't know	73 (24.33)	20 (12.12)	
Bones	Yes	113 (37.66)	27 (16.36)	0.01
	No	94 (31.33)	94 (56.96)	
	Don't know	93 (31)	44 (26.66)	
Liver	Yes	257 (85.66)	103 (62.42)	0.04
	No	12 (4)	1 (0.60)	
	Don't know	31 (10.33)	66 (40)	
All of the above	Yes	216 (72)	97 (58.78)	0.03
	No	35 (11.66)	12 (7.27)	
	Don't know	49 (16.33)	56 (33.93)	
Purpose of organ donation	Social responsibility	202 (67.33)	12 (7.27)	0.03
	To save other's life	67 (22.33)	78 (47.27)	
	Sympathy	31 (10.33)	75 (45.45)	
Organ donation is unsafe?	Yes	213 (71)	123 (74.54)	0.4
	No	17 (5.66)	2 (1.21)	
	Don't know	70 (23.33)	40 (24.24)	
donated organs could be misused	Yes	149 (49.66)	61 (36.96)	
	No	91 (30.33)	34 (20.60)	
	Don't know	60 (20)	70 (42.42)	
Would you donate the organ	NO	109 (36.33)	56 (33.93)	0.02
	Will think about it	95 (31.66)	27 (13.36)	
	Would definitely want to	96 (32)	82 (49.69)	
Feels donor not live long	Yes	267 (89)	142 (86.06)	0.01
	No	21 (7)	2 (1.21)	
	Don't know	12 (4)	21 (12.72)	

Table 3. Respondents' attitudes and willingness toward organ donation.

Question	Options	Farmers n=300 (%)	Laborers n=165 (%)	p value
Does organ donation involve any risks?	Yes	239 (79.66)	123 (74.54)	0.03
	No	34 (11.33)	2 (1.21)	
	Don't know	27 (9)	40 (24.24)	
Whom would you like to donate to	Friend	72 (24)	41 (24.84)	0.03
	Family member	119 (39.66)	75 (45.45)	
	Anyone needed	32 (10.66)	11 (6.66)	
	Physically disabled	11 (3.66)	2 (1.21)	
	Same religion	16 (5.33)	3 (1.81)	
	Any religion	50 (16.66)	33 (20)	

Should organ donation be promoted?	Yes	269 (89.66)	132 (80)	0.06
	No	3 (1)	3 (1.81)	
	Don't know	28 (9.33)	30 (18.18)	
Have you ever donated blood?	Yes	190 (63.33)	62 (37.57)	0.001
	No	70 (23.33)	74 (44.84)	
	Don't know	44 (14.66)	29 (17.57)	
Do you think it's important to bury my body "whole"?	Yes	179 (59.66)	119 (72.12)	0.01
	No	93 (31)	26 (15.75)	
	Don't know	28 (9.33)	20 (12.12)	

Table 3 depicts respondents' attitudes on organ donation; question 1 asks whether organ donation is risky? This question is about the feelings of participants, farmers, and laborers who picked this choice. Yes, 213 (71%) and 123 (74.54%), respectively.

We checked Attitude and the willingness of organ donation by the question Whom would you like to donate to farmers in responded Family member 119 (39.66%) and Laborers 75 (45.45%) and the organ donation to "Any Religion", farmers responded 50 (16.66%) and Laborers 33 (20%). As an Indian citizen with a social obligation to society to assist better people's lives, I checked this criterion using the question Should organ donation be promoted? Farmers opted YES 269 (89.66%), while laborers voted NO 132 (80%). In question: Have you ever donated blood? Farmers 190 (63.33%) chose yes, while laborers 74 (44.84%) chose no. Response to the question "Do you think it's important to bury my body "whole"? 179 (59.66%) farmers and 119 (72.12%) laborers said YES.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study aimed to analyze the knowledge and attitudes toward organ donation among farmers and laborers in Andhra Pradesh. Health care workers play an important role in educating and raising awareness about organ donation in a community. In our research of 465 individuals, 136 were female and 329 were male. This cross-sectional survey successfully

assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and desire to donate organs. Many people die while on the waiting list because of the lengthy wait time, or they grow too ill for the transplant and are removed from the list. To alleviate the organ scarcity, live donation is being encouraged. Countries in Asia and the Middle East are projected to dominate in living donor organ transplantation. (LDLT)[12,13]. In each health system, public awareness of organ donation has a basic impact on the organ transplantation program: knowledge and perceptions about organ donation are favorably related with attitudes toward donation, readiness to donate, and donor registration [14,15].

According to research, the most significant factors discovered in this survey, which were also included in the multivariate analysis, are mostly related to three aspects: The family, physical manipulation, and religion [16]. The key factors that influenced the organ donation were religion of the recipient and the assurance that the donor organs would be treated respectfully [17]. At the family level, research has shown that addressing the matter with family members enhances the chance of being supportive of organ donation[18,19]. Most respondents appreciated their family members' opinions and preferred to donate their organs to relatives or friends rather than strangers [20]. These findings suggest that both farmers and laborers have some concerns about the risks associated with organ donation, but a significant proportion of them are willing to

donate to family members and people of any religion. The majority of farmers and a sizable proportion of laborers support the promotion of organ donation. However, a larger percentage of laborers compared to farmers consider it extremely important to have their body buried "whole," which could be a barrier to organ donation. These insights can help inform targeted educational and awareness campaigns to address the concerns and misconceptions about organ donation, particularly among the laborer population, and encourage more individuals to consider becoming organ donors. The majority of the respondents in our study agreed that the government should initiate strategies to motivate organ donation by providing priorities in the beneficiary schemes in response of question "Should organ donation be promoted?". The differences in attitudes and beliefs towards organ donation between farmers and laborers likely reflect deeper socioeconomic and cultural influences. Factors such as education level, access to healthcare information, religious and traditional practices, and community perceptions may all play a role in shaping these perspectives. A more comprehensive assessment of the social, economic, and cultural determinants of organ donation attitudes within these populations would be valuable. The high proportion of both farmers and laborers who perceive organ donation as risky suggests that there are widespread misconceptions about the safety, medical procedures, and outcomes of organ donation. Targeted education campaigns, utilizing trusted community leaders and healthcare providers, could help dispel these myths and allay concerns about the risks involved. Providing transparent and easily accessible information about the organ donation process, success rates, and safeguards in place could help build trust and confidence.

The higher willingness to donate to family members compared to people of any religion suggests the importance of community and kinship ties in the decision-making process. Engaging with local community organizations,

religious leaders, and social influencers could be an effective way to promote organ donation within these tightly-knit groups. Developing outreach strategies that emphasize the collective benefits to the community, rather than just individual donors, may resonate more with these populations. The stronger preference for "whole body" burial among laborers highlights the need to understand and address the religious or cultural beliefs that may be barriers to organ donation. Collaborating with religious leaders and community elders to find ways to reconcile these beliefs with the importance of organ donation could be a crucial step. Exploring alternative burial or memorial practices that could accommodate organ donation may help alleviate some of these concerns. Given the differences observed between farmers and laborers, a one-size-fits-all approach to organ donation promotion is unlikely to be effective. Developing targeted interventions and monitoring their impact on specific socioeconomic and cultural groups would be essential for designing more impactful and inclusive organ donation programs. Continuous evaluation and feedback loops could help refine these approaches and ensure they are meeting the needs and addressing the concerns of diverse communities. By taking a deeper dive into the socioeconomic and cultural factors influencing organ donation attitudes, addressing misconceptions and fears, fostering community-based approaches, and accommodating religious and burial beliefs, India can work towards increasing organ donation rates in a sustainable and equitable manner. This multifaceted approach will be crucial for improving access to life-saving organ transplants and positively impacting the lives of people in need.

Recommendations

Organizing campaigns and activities to raise awareness about organ donation and transplantation can assist farmers and laborers improve their knowledge and attitudes.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Ethics statement

The studies involving human participants were reviewed and approved by Medical Research Ethics Committee, Maharajah's Institute of Medical Sciences, Vizianagaram, Andhra Pradesh, India. The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no any potential conflict of interest.

References:

1. Donors1.org (Internet). Philadelphia: Gift of Life Donor Program [quoted on May 19, 2020]. Available at <https://www.donors1.org/learn-about-organ-donation/why-donate/organs-tissues-for-transplant>.
2. Tokalak I, Kut A, Moray G, Emiroglu R, Erdal R, Karakayali H, Haberal M. Knowledge and attitudes of high school students related to organ donation and transplantation: a cross-sectional survey in Turkey. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl* 2006; 17: 491-496 [PMID: 17186682]
3. Wakefield CE, Watts KJ, Homewood J, Meiser B, Siminoff LA. Attitudes toward organ donation and donor behavior: a review of the international literature. *Prog Transplant* 2010; 20: 380-391 [PMID: 21265292 DOI: 10.7182/prtr.20.4.p54651601pg80183]
4. Rudge C, Matesanz R, Delmonico FL, Chapman J. International practices of organ donation. *Br J Anaesth*. 2012;108:i48-i55. doi:10.1093/bja/aer399
5. Vanholder R, Domínguez-Gil B, Busic M, et al. Organ donation and transplantation: a multi-stakeholder call to action. *Nature reviews. Nephrology*. 2021;17:554-568. doi:10.1038/s41581-021-00425-3
6. Alsharidah DS, Al-Dossari FS, AlMahmoud N, et al. Assessment of knowledge and attitude toward organ donation among the Saudi population in Riyadh city. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl*. 2018;29:1326-1332. doi:10.4103/1319-2442.248304
7. Rithalia A, McDaid C, Suekarran S, Myers L, Sowden A. Impact of presumed consent for organ donation on donation rates: A systematic review. *BMJ* 2009;338:a3162.
8. Aastha Ahuja. Here Is Why India Needs More People To Step Up For The Cause Of Organ Donation. [Updated 2018 November 2; Cited 2020 May 23]. Available from <https://sites.ndtv.com/moretogive/india-needs-people-step-cause-organ-donation-2695/>
9. Mekahli D, Liutkus A, Fargue S, Ranchin B, Cochat P. Survey of first-year medical students to assess their knowledge and attitudes toward organ transplantation and donation. *Transplant Proc* 2009; 41:634-8.
10. Schaeffner ES, Windisch W, Freidel K, Breitenfeldt K, Winkelmayr WC. Knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among medical students and physicians. *Transplantation* 2004; 77:1714-8.
11. Chakradhar K, Doshi D, Srikanth Reddy B, Kulkarni S, Padma Reddy M, Sruthi Reddy S. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Organ Donation among Indian Dental Students. *Int J Organ Transplant Med*. 2016;7(1):28-35.
12. Keten HS, Keten D, Ucer H, Cerit M, Isik O, Miniksar OH, Ersoy O. Knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of mosque imams regarding organ donation. *Ann Transplant* 2014; 19: 598-603 [PMID: 25402268 DOI: 10.12659/AOT.891370]

13. Shaheen FA, Souqiyyeh MZ. Current obstacles to organ transplant in Middle Eastern countries. *Exp Clin Transplant* 2015; 13 Suppl 1: 1-3 [PMID: 25894118 DOI: 10.6002/ect.mesot2014.L4] [PMID: 31033855 DOI: 10.1097/TP.0000000000002622]
14. Tokalak I, Kut A, Moray G, Emiroglu R, Erdal R, Karakayali H, Haberal M. Knowledge and attitudes of high school students related to organ donation and transplantation: a cross-sectional survey in Turkey. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl* 2006; 17: 491-496 [PMID: 17186682]
15. Wakefield CE, Watts KJ, Homewood J, Meiser B, Siminoff LA. Attitudes toward organ donation and donor behavior: a review of the international literature. *Prog Transplant* 2010; 20: 380-391 [PMID: 21265292 DOI: 10.7182/prtr.20.4.p54651601pg80183]
16. Ríos A, López-Navas AI, Navalón JC, Martínez-Alarcón L, Ayala-García MA, Sebastián-Ruiz MJ, MoyaFaz F, Garrido G, Ramirez P, Parrilla P. The Latin American population in Spain and organ donation. Attitude toward deceased organ donation and organ donation rates. *Transpl Int* 2015; 28: 437-447 [PMID: 25557362 DOI: 10.1111/tri.12511]
17. Saleem T, Ishaque S, Habib N, Hussain SS, Jawed A, et al. Knowledge, attitudes and practices survey on organ donation among a selected adult population of Pakistan. *BMC Medical Ethics* 2009, 10: 5 doi: 10.1186/1472-6939-10-5
18. de Groot J, van Hoek M, Hoedemaekers C, Hoitsma A, Smeets W, Vernooij-Dassen M, van Leeuwen E. Decision making on organ donation: the dilemmas of relatives of potential brain dead donors. *BMC Med Ethics* 2015; 16: 64 [PMID: 26383919 DOI: 10.1186/s12910-015-0057-1]
19. Delgado J, Molina-Pérez A, Shaw D, Rodríguez-Arias D. The Role of the Family in Deceased Organ Procurement: A Guide for Clinicians and Policymakers. *Transplantation* 2019; 103: e112-e118
20. Lei L, Deng J, Zhang H, Dong H, Luo Y, Luo Y. Level of Organ Donation-Related Knowledge and Attitude and Willingness Toward Organ Donation Among a Group of University Students in Western China. *Transplant Proc* 2018; 50: 2924-2931 [PMID: 30577149 DOI: 10.1016/j.transproceed.2018.02.095]